

DEVELOPMENT AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF PEDIATRIC LOZENGE FORMULATIONS CONTAINING MELATONIN

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INTRODUCTION

Sleep-related complaints of pediatric patients include difficulty falling asleep, waking up at night, snoring, excessive daytime sleepiness, and daytime dysfunction. Melatonin is commonly used to treat sleep difficulties. Melatonin use is also important in improving symptoms other than sleep problems, such as anxiety, depression, pain and gastrointestinal dysfunction. Lozenges have advantages such as being easy-to-administer dosage forms for children, not needing to be swallowed, being easy to change their contents and customize for the patient, having a long disintegration time, keeping the active ingredient in contact with the buccal mucosa for a very long time, and being prepared in different ways and given to children like candy.

KEYWORDS: Sleep disorder, Pediatric, Melatonin, Lozange

RELEVANCE OF THE TOPIC

This study aimed to develop pediatric formulations for use in the treatment of sleep disorders.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Development and *in vitro* characterization of melatonin lozenges for sleep disorder in children.

RESEARCH METHODS

To prepare the lozenges, sugar, glucose and citric acid were used. Lemon, pineapple orange, cola and vanilla flavors were used to add flavor. Additionally, curcumin, a natural substance, was used to color the formulations. Melatonin lozenges were examined in terms of diameter/thickness, weight deviation, hardness, friability, dissolution time, content uniformity, *in vitro* dissolution behavior, microbiological analysis, moisture content. Studies were carried out at Ege University Faculty of Pharmacy and MEKSMAR Natural & Healthy Products Production & Marketing Co. Ltd.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

UV Spectrophotometer method was developed and the calibration curve was drawn (Figure1). Average weight of lozenges was found 3,51 g. Average disintegration time of lozenges was found 13 min. *In vitro* dissolution profile of optimum lozange formulation was presented in Figure 2. Microbiological analysis results were found suitable (Table1).

Figure 1: Calibration Curve

Figure 2: Dissolution Profile of Lozenge Containing Melatonin

Table 1: Microbiological Analysis Results

Mirobiological Analysis	Analysis Method	Specifications	Results
Total Aerobic Bacteria	Ph. Eur. 2.6.12	$<10^4$ cfu/g	60 cfu/g
Yeast - Mold	Ph. Eur. 2.6.12	$<10^3$ cfu/g	0
E.coli	Ph. Eur. 2.6.12	Not	0

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